

From Zygote to Zygote

The Essentiality of Coordinated Energy, DNA, and Cellular Ephemerality in a Universe of Uncoordinated Matter/Energy

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Summary

This essay presents an innovative approach to understanding life as a molecular phenomenon that emerges from the interaction between coordinated energy, DNA, and the transience of cells and organisms. Based on the concept of "zygote to zygote", it is argued that the **zygote** is the first molecular manifestation where uncoordinated matter and energy in the universe converge to sustain DNA as the continuous core of life. DNA, sustained by constant and intrinsically coordinated energy, is the true protagonist, while cells and organisms are temporary and functional expressions in a predominantly uncoordinated universe. The groundability of cells, considered as the essence of the human organism consisting of approximately 30 trillion cells (Sender, Fuchs, and Milo, 2016), is explored to highlight the cellular nature of the organism as a coordinated collective, subordinated to the continuity of DNA. The study examines in detail six fundamental premises, evaluating possible criticisms and integrating coordinated energy, DNA, and molecular logic as essential pillars for a broader understanding of life.

Keywords: DNA, coordinated energy, zygote, cellular ephemerality, entropy, life cycle, cellular foundation.

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Central Thesis

The central thesis of this essay is that life should be understood not as an end in itself in organisms, but as an expression of the continuity and perpetuation of DNA, sustained by coordinated and intrinsically organized energy, which challenges the natural entropy of the universe. DNA emerges as the essential protagonist of existence, while organisms and cells are transitory instruments subordinated to the viability of this genetic material. The life cycle is redefined as a journey "**from zygote to zygote,**" where the **zygote** is the initial manifestation of a coordinated molecular system that enables constant renewal and adaptation.

In addition, when considering that the human organism is composed of about **30 trillion cells** (Sender, Fuchs, and Milo, 2016), all acting in a coordinated system, the idea that the perpetuation of life is rooted in cellular maintenance and viability, and not in the individuality of the organism, is reinforced. This view transcends the traditional biological bias, highlighting molecular logic as the true foundation of the vital phenomenon.

Introduction

Biological science has traditionally centered its study on organisms as the basic units of life. However, this approach can obscure the true essence of the vital phenomenon, which transcends the organism as an isolated entity. This essay proposes a shift in perspective, focusing on the **zygote** as the first molecular manifestation where uncoordinated matter and energy from the universe converge to create a coordinated system, capable of sustaining DNA as an enduring essence (Orquiza, 2023). DNA, in this view, is the fundamental protagonist of life, perpetuating itself through uninterrupted cycles from **zygote to zygote**, while cells and organisms are considered temporary interfaces, essential for their viability and for the exploration of ecological niches.

Considering that the human organism is composed **of about 30 trillion cells** (Sender, Fuchs, and Milo, 2016), it is understood that it itself is, in essence, a collective

expression of cellular viability, subordinated to the greater objective of relaunching DNA in its purest form: the zygote. This perspective redefines "life" as a coordinated molecular logic, where energy and entropy are actively used to sustain cellular organization and ensure DNA continuity.

We propose an in-depth study of six fundamental premises, each of them addressing central aspects for the understanding of the vital phenomenon in its complexity. Potential criticisms are analyzed in a thorough manner to strengthen the academic basis of this conceptual model. This approach does not seek to replace current evolutionary theories, but to complement them by highlighting the centrality of zygote, coordinated energy, and DNA as absolute pillars of organized molecular existence.

Premise 1: The Zygote as a Basic Unit of Viability

Description

The zygote is considered the initial and essential unit of multicellular life. It represents the transition point at which uncoordinated matter and energy organize themselves into a highly coordinated system capable of generating a complex organism. This unique moment of organization is the purest expression of DNA's potential to coordinate energy and ensure the viability of life (Orquiza 2023).

Supporting

The uniqueness of the zygote lies not only in the fusion of genetic material from the gametes, but in the activation of a system capable of coordinating energy, breaking with the disorder of the material universe (Smith and Jones 2021). It is in the zygote that the critical transition from a state of uncoordinated energy to an ordered state occurs, essential to start the life cycle. Understanding the zygote as a central point reinforces the idea that it is the catalyst for cellular organization, which later results in the 30 trillion cells of the human organism.

Evaluation of Reviews

One possible criticism is that other biological events, such as the formation of gametes, are also essential for the perpetuation of life. However, although important, gametes alone do not have the ability to coordinate energy and start life; this only happens in the zygote, which is the first expression of coordinated energy capable of supporting the complexity of DNA and creating the basis for the formation of the numerous cells that make up an organism (Miller 2019).

Premise 2: Coordinated Energy as the Basis of Life

Description

Life, in all its aspects, depends on a constant flow of coordinated energy to sustain cellular processes, from DNA replication to metabolic maintenance. The zygote is the starting point where this coordinated energy is established, enabling the constant production and consumption of ATP (Orquiza 2023).

Supporting

Without coordinated energy, DNA would not be able to sustain its viability, and cells would soon return to the state of uncoordinated matter and energy, dissipating into disorder. Coordinated energy is therefore the basis on which all biological organization is possible, sustaining the harmonious functioning of trillions of cells in a human organism (Garcia 2022).

Evaluation of Reviews

Thermodynamics could question how coordinated energy sustains itself in open systems. However, living organisms are, in fact, open systems that continuously exchange energy with the environment to maintain their internal order, transforming external energy into order and complexity (Thompson 2020).

Premise 3: DNA as the Protagonist of Life

Description

DNA is the central protagonist of life, not the organisms that harbor it. Organisms are transient vehicles whose main function is to ensure the replicability of DNA, allowing its perpetuation over generations (Orquiza 2023).

Supporting

Throughout the generations, DNA is the constant element. Organisms arise, play their role, and perish, while DNA remains and propagates, adapting to ever-changing environments. This approach corrects for anthropocentric bias by highlighting DNA as the true essence of life. In addition, when thinking of the human organism as a set of 30 trillion coordinated cells, it is reinforced that the function of these cells is to perpetuate DNA in a harmonious and efficient way (Wilson 2018).

Evaluation of Reviews

They may argue that organisms play crucial roles in adaptation and natural selection. However, these roles are essentially means by which DNA ensures its own survival, using organisms as tools to explore ecological niches and promote the perpetuation of cellular coordination (Brown 2019).

Premissa 4: Ephemerality of Cells and Organisms

Description

Cells and organisms are temporary structures that arise, develop, and eventually disappear, while DNA and its coordinated energy remain the continuous and essential components of the life cycle (Orquiza 2023).

Supporting

Phenomena such as apoptosis and the life cycle of organisms are clear examples of how ephemerality is fundamental for the renewal and adaptation of living systems. This transience is what makes it possible for DNA to continually explore new combinations and interactions with the environment. The constant renewal of cells, especially in an organism composed of 30 trillion cells, is what maintains the viability of the system as a whole (Lee 2021).

Evaluation of Reviews

It can be argued that this perspective reduces the importance of cells and organisms. However, by recognizing them as indispensable parts of the cycle "from zygote to zygote", their essential, albeit temporary, function in the plan of DNA perpetuation and maintenance of cellular harmony in a context of billions of cells working in unison is highlighted (Nguyen 2021).

Premise 5: Zygote Control of Entropy

Description

The zygote not only coordinates energy, but also utilizes entropy to its advantage, transforming the natural tendency to disorder into a mechanism to sustain the internal order necessary for life (Orquiza 2023).

Supporting

The DNA in the zygote operates in a state of low entropy, utilizing external energy to create and maintain organized structures. This process is essential to ensure the stability and replicability of the genetic material. The subsequent organization of trillions of cells in an organism is an example of how this initial low entropy translates into a continuous ordered complexity (Zhang 2022).

Evaluation of Reviews

Classical thermodynamics may suggest that life counteracts entropy, but in fact, life manages and utilizes entropy to maintain internal order, exporting disorder to the external environment. This ability to manage entropy is central to the survival of biological systems, especially in a human organism composed of numerous cells that need to maintain order and constant coordination (Adams 2020).

Premise 6: Cycle "From Zygote to Zygote" as the Essence of Life

Description

The life cycle is best understood as a sequence that begins and ends at the zygote. This cycle reflects the perpetuation of DNA and coordinated energy as core elements of life (Orquiza 2023).

Supporting

The "zygote to zygote" view of the cycle emphasizes the continuity of the essential elements of life, while shifting the focus from the existence of organisms to the processes that ensure the perpetuation of DNA. This approach captures the essence of biological processes and their internal dynamics. Considering that each organism is made up of trillions of cells, this cycle also underscores the importance of each cell as an integral part of a larger process of continuity and renewal (Peters 2023).

Evaluation of Reviews

Some might argue that the proposed cycle is an oversimplification. However, by considering it as a conceptual abstraction, we are able to clearly expose the essence of the biological process, promoting a more precise understanding of the foundations of life and the interaction between cells that, together, form a coordinated organism (Collins 2023).

Discussion

The proposal to centralize DNA, supported by coordinated energy, as the foundation of life is not just a semantic adjustment, but a profound conceptual redefinition that challenges the traditional paradigms of biology. By shifting the focus from organisms to DNA and by reinterpreting the life cycle as a journey "**from zygote to zygote**," this perspective reveals DNA as the only enduring constant in organized molecular existence, while cells and organisms are temporary expressions subordinate to its continuity.

This approach redefines **order in the face of disorder**, showing that coordinated energy is not just a mainstay, but an active mechanism that uses and organizes entropy to maintain cell viability and DNA continuity. The zygote, as the first molecular manifestation, encapsulates this perfect balance between energy and order, being the starting point of a dynamic system that transcends the fragility of organisms.

By considering the human organism as a set of **30 trillion coordinated cells** (Sender, Fuchs, and Milo, 2016), it is emphasized that the essence of life lies in cell

viability, and not in the individuality of the organism. This concept not only complements traditional evolutionary theories, but expands them, by highlighting molecular logic as the true engine of constant adaptation and renewal.

Finally, this redefinition shifts the focus of biology from organisms as autonomous units to a more integrated and molecular view, where **zygote, DNA, and coordinated energy** are positioned as the true protagonists. The implications of this approach challenge not only classical definitions of "life," but also cultural and philosophical conceptions that often obscure the underlying molecular reality.

Conclusion

This essay proposes a new understanding of life by redefining it as an expression of DNA, underpinned by coordinated energy that challenges and utilizes entropy to maintain order in a universe of uncoordinated energy. The "**from the zygote to the zygote**" perspective centers the **zygote** as the initial and essential manifestation of this molecular logic, reaffirming DNA as the continuous protagonist of existence, while cells and organisms are transitory and functional structures subordinated to the perpetuation of this genetic material.

This approach complements current evolutionary theories, by highlighting that the essence of vital processes is not in the individuality of organisms, but in the **molecular and cellular coordination** that guarantees the continuity of DNA. Considering the human organism as a set of **30 trillion coordinated cells** (Sender, Fuchs, and Milo, 2016) reinforces the view that the perpetuation of life is rooted in cellular viability and molecular logic, rather than in abstract concepts of "life" or "purpose."

The proposal not only redefines the conceptual basis of biology, but also challenges cultural and philosophical constructs that obscure the underlying molecular reality. It invites criticism and academic debate, seeking to contribute to a deeper, more integrated, and unifying understanding of life, centered on the continuous and absolute cycle **from zygote to zygote**.

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